

METHODS OF DEVELOPING CREATIVE ABILITIES IN CHORAL CONDUCTING

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Annotation: This article analyzes effective methods for developing students' creative abilities in the discipline of choral conducting. In particular, the possibilities of forming musical and creative abilities through the use of innovative approaches, interactive methods, and technologies in the pedagogical process are considered. The study highlights the importance of using new methodological methods in the development of musical taste, rhythmic sense, and aesthetic sensitivity in teaching choral conducting. In addition, the methodological aspects of strengthening coherence and creative cooperation in working with choral groups are analyzed.

Keywords: Choral conducting, creative abilities, pedagogical methodology, innovative approach, musical taste, aesthetic education, interactive teaching, creative cooperation.

Introduction.

Art has a miraculous power that enriches a person's soul, expands his worldview, and reveals his creative abilities. In particular, the art of music plays a special role in human life. The discipline of choral conducting has a special place in this type of art. Because choral conducting is an important tool not only in the field of music, but also in expanding the creative potential of the individual. The process of working with a choral team is not only the performance of musical works, but also the upbringing of artistic and aesthetic feelings, the development of creative thinking.

Today, one of the main tasks of the education system is to educate creative youth, to reveal and develop their musical abilities. The implementation of this task in the discipline of choral conducting depends on the approach of teachers. It is extremely important to support creativity in the educational process, develop students' musical feelings, and develop their thinking skills by introducing modern pedagogical methods and innovative technologies.

This article is devoted to the study of approaches aimed at developing creative abilities in the discipline of choral conducting. In this process, the influence of choral art and the pedagogical significance of creative cooperation are revealed. Because choral conducting is not only music, but also a kind of creative school.

Methodology.

The development of creative abilities is not only a complex and multifaceted process of identifying natural talent, but also its formation and direction. In the discipline of choral conducting, it is necessary to establish the correct methodological foundations to ensure the effectiveness of this process. In particular, it is extremely important to organize the pedagogical process taking into account the individual characteristics of students and create an environment that inspires creativity.

At the heart of the methodological approach are innovative and interactive methods aimed at forming creative thinking in the musical and educational process. In particular, the use of game pedagogical technologies, training through musical dialogue, and creative experiments in choral performance are among the most effective methods for developing creative abilities. Such methods not only cultivate musical taste and rhythmic sense, but also form creative initiative in students.

Also, in the discipline of choral conducting, it is important to teach students a culture of musical cooperation and teamwork. In this process, emphasis is placed on methods that develop a deep understanding of the role of each participant and the ability to appreciate the artistic value of collective performance. In particular, the interpretation of choral works based on the “creative laboratory” method, joint analysis of voice parts, and the search for new artistic ideas during the performance process create a favorable opportunity to improve creative abilities. In addition, the use of multimedia technologies in the discipline of choral conducting opens up new horizons for the development of creativity. The implementation of the process of notational analysis of choral works, visualization of rhythmic schemes, and work on sound balance in an interactive format using special programs serves to improve students' musical abilities.

Thus, in order to successfully organize the process of developing creative abilities in the discipline of choral conducting, it is necessary to combine various methodological approaches. These methods serve to further reveal the creative potential of students and expand their musical aesthetic outlook.

Discussion.

When we analyze the methodological approaches to developing creative abilities in the discipline of choral conducting, the importance of this process in ensuring not only musical skill, but also general personal development is revealed. Creative approaches play an important role in ensuring the specific characteristics of the choral ensemble, its internal coherence and harmony. In

this regard, it is necessary to develop the creative potential of each conductor, choir student and team members to the maximum.

First of all, enriching the teaching process in the discipline of choral conducting with innovative pedagogical approaches is an effective tool for increasing the creative thinking of students. In choral art, creative abilities are not limited only to technical skills, but also aspects such as aesthetic understanding, self-expression and artistic sensitivity are important. Therefore, in choral conducting classes, interactive methods, musical hearing, note analysis, rhythmic exercises and compositional elements are required. These methods not only enrich the musical experience, but also reveal the creative potential of students.

Secondly, the issue of developing creative cooperation, team spirit and mutual trust, which are important in choral performance, also deserves special attention. It is necessary to pay attention to the behavior, attitude to music and artistic expression of each member of the choral team. The role of the conductor in the development of creative abilities, the adaptation of the team to each other and the development of musical perception is invaluable. The success of the choir depends on its leadership, the complementarity of its members and the artistic image they create together.

At the same time, the use of technologies in the development of creative abilities in choral conducting also plays a great role. Modern multimedia tools, music programs and interactive platforms expand students' creative approaches, creating new opportunities for them. Depicting notes and rhythm, controlling the sound balance, analyzing choral works in digital format and performing exercises online open up new ways of musical expression for choir students.

However, in order for all methodological approaches to be effective, they require taking into account the individual characteristics of students and the pedagogical experience of the teacher. It is necessary to look at each student as a unique person, identify his creative potential and choose an approach that is appropriate for them. In ensuring creative development in the discipline of choral conducting, the teacher's intuition, emotions and pedagogical skills play an important role.

In conclusion, when methodological approaches to developing creative abilities in the discipline of choral conducting are implemented in a broad and complex, but effective system, students' abilities in understanding, expressing and performing musical art are revealed. By properly organizing this process,

supporting creativity and forming a team spirit, it is possible to achieve significant results in the discipline of choral conducting.

Conclusion.

The development of creative abilities in the discipline of choral conducting is not only an important component of musical education, but also one of the main tools for ensuring the personal and artistic development of students. This process is based on the principles of creativity-oriented education, in which it is important to teach each student to deeply feel the musical image, express it artistically and think creatively.

The analyzed approaches indicate the need to use integrated methods in the development of creative abilities in choral conducting classes. In addition to acquiring technical knowledge, choral art also develops musical and aesthetic abilities. Therefore, the use of innovative pedagogical technologies, the introduction of interactive classes, the promotion of collective creativity and the formation of creative cooperation in the process of providing students with musical experience are of great importance.

In addition, choral conducting classes not only develop musical skills, but also enrich students socially and psychologically. In the process of working in a choral team, students learn to listen to each other, understand each other, and combine creative ideas. This develops qualities that are important not only in the field of music, but also in other aspects of life.

At the same time, each approach to developing students' abilities in choral conducting requires an individual approach. The creative potential of each student is different, and the teacher's skill and pedagogical intuition play a great role in their development.

In conclusion, the development of creative abilities in choral conducting is a complex but inspiring process. Through this process, students understand musical aesthetics, learn to express themselves through art, and develop as individuals. Thus, choral conducting is not only an art form, but also an important tool for the formation of a creative personality.

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